

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF PLATINUM(II) COMPLEXES*

Complex/Stoichiometry	Colour	Λ_M ohm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ cm ²	Anal. sis % ; Found/(Calcd.)					$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹ (e)
			Pt	N	Cl	C	H	
[Pt(EDTA)en]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Lemon yellow	225.8	31.4 (81.55)	8.8 (9.06)	11.2 (11.49)	28.4 (28.30)	3.9 (3.88)	50000(17140), 37740(10020), 30779(62)
[Pt(EDTA)tn]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Yellow	215.1	31.1 (80.85)	8.9 (8.86)	11.0 (11.28)	24.8 (24.68)	4.2 (4.11)	
[Pt(EDTA)pn]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Light yellow	228.3	30.5 (80.85)	8.9 (8.86)	10.9 (11.28)	24.2 (24.68)	4.3 (4.11)	
[Pt(EDTA)apy]Cl ₂ C ₁₃ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Light yellow	229.2	29.3 (29.91)	8.7 (8.69)	10.6 (10.89)	27.4 (27.61)	3.2 (3.37)	50000(17760). 39220(10640). 30770(1705)
[Pt(EDTA)bipy]Cl ₂ C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Reddish yellow	a	28.0 (27.81)	7.6 (7.84)	9.4 (9.94)	38.7 (38.61)	3.4 (3.86)	
[Pt(EDTA)phen]Cl ₂ C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	Lemon yellow	a	26.3 (26.42)	7.2 (7.59)	9.2 (9.62)	35.7 (35.77)	3.1 (3.25)	

a Conductance could not be measured due to low solubility of the compound in water.

* Abbreviations : en = ethylenediamine, tn = trimethylenediamine, pn = propylenediamine, apy = 3-aminopyridine, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridyl and phen = orthophenanthroline.

groups are free. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (ring) stretch of 2,2'-bipyridyl, orthophenanthroline and 3-aminopyridine occurs at 1582, 1558 and 1590 cm⁻¹, respectively^{7,8}. In the complexes, this band undergoes a positive shift by 30-38 cm⁻¹. This is indicative of nitrogen coordination of these ligands. The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ vibration of ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine, propylenediamine and 3-aminopyridine occurs at 1620, 1620, 1620 and 1590 cm⁻¹, respectively^{8,9}. In the platinum(II) complexes this band shifts to lower wave number by 10-45 cm⁻¹. This indicates the nitrogen coordination of these amines. Thus, the complexes are straightforward four-coordinate.

The electronic spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The complexes exhibit three bands around 30000, 38000 and 50000 cm⁻¹. Only in the ethylenediamine complex the first band has low molar extinction coefficient (52 litre mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and this band can be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ transition. The molar extinction coefficients of other bands are very high and these bands may be assigned to intraligand, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions¹⁰.

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References

1. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", Prentice Hall, N. Y., 1960, p. 38; K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1969, p. 238; G. W. WATT and D. S. KLETT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1278; R. E. SILVERS and J. C. BAILER, JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 174; M. L. MORRIS and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 5178.
2. D. H. BUSCH and J. C. BAILER, JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 716.
3. A. SYAMAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 513.

4. W. E. COOKEY and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, 5, 208.
5. A. SYAMAL and B. K. GUPTA, *Transition Metal Chem.*, 1983, 8, 36.
6. M. M. JONES, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry", Prentice Hall, New York, 1964, p. 254.
7. R. G. INSKHEP, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, 24, 763; A. A. SCHILT and R. C. TAYLOR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1959, 9, 211.
8. A. R. MATRITZKY, A. R. HANDS and R. A. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3165.
9. L. SEGAL and F. V. EGGERTON, *Applied Spectrosc.*, 1961, 15, 112.
10. A. SYAMAL and O. P. SINGHAL, *Transition Metal Chem.*, 1979, 4, 179.

Screening of Metal Complexes for Biological Activity. Part V : Synthesis and Biological Studies on Zinc(II) Complexes with Various Amides

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BIOCHEMICAL and medicinal significance of simple zinc(II) complexes has been discussed by many workers¹⁻³. However, coordination complexes of zinc(II) are yet to be subjected to these studies. So, as a part of our investigation on synthesis of biologically active metal complexes⁴⁻⁵, we report here preparation, characterization and a few pharmacological aspects viz., toxicity and effects on central nervous system (CNS) of some zinc(II) complexes of nicotinamide (nic), N-methyl-propanamide (Nmpa) and benzamide (bza).

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NOTES

Experimental

Zinc(II) salts (dissolved or suspended in ethanol) were refluxed with three fold excess of the amide on water bath for 18-20 hr with continued stirring and the reaction mixture was kept in freeze for another 6 hr for crystallisation. The resulting complexes were filtered, washed thoroughly with water and ethanol successively to remove unreacted metal salt and amide, respectively. Purified complexes were dried at 110° in air oven and subsequently subjected to various physico chemical and biological studies.

Biological activity :

Acute toxicity : The customary yardstick of acute toxicity is LD₅₀ (the single dose killing 50% of the experimental population). For toxicological studies mice of either sex weighing 18-22 g were taken into groups of five each and kept at room temperature of 24±2. They were deprived of food for 16 hr and then administered graded doses of the test compound suspended in 0.2 ml of gum acacia, intraperitoneally. The mortality of mice in each group was recorded during the next 24 hr and approximate LD₅₀ was calculated. The results of toxicological investigations are recorded in Table 1.

Central nervous system (CNS) activity : Behavioural and neurological effects (effects on CNS) produced by the test compounds were studied on two groups of mice each having 5 animals. All the animals were of approximately the same age and

weight. Each mouse was given 1/5 LD₅₀ dose of test compound intraperitoneally. All the animals were continuously observed for 2 hr after drug administration for any evidence of stimulation or depression of central nervous system. The observed neurological profiles are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Analytical, spectral and pharmacological results of the complexes have been recorded in Table 1. On the basis of elemental analysis and conductance, the complexes may be represented as [ZnX₂L₂]ⁿ where X=NO₃, 0.5SO₄²⁻, 0.5C₂O₄²⁻ and L=nic, Nmpa, bza.

IR spectra :

In free amides two N-H stretching bands resulting from asymmetric and symmetric stretchings are observed as doublets around 3350 and 3120 cm⁻¹. In bza and Nmpa complexes these bands show considerable negative shift indicating coordination through amide nitrogen. Further, disappearance of N-H out of plane bending vibration of these amides (around 850 cm⁻¹) in their complexes confirms the coordination through amide nitrogen⁶. On the other hand very small negative shift in both N-H stretching bands has been observed in nic complexes, which is due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding of amide and not because of its coordination with metal. That nicotinamide coordinates

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, SPECTRAL AND BIOLOGICAL RESULTS OF ZINC COMPLEXES

Sl. Compound No.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				Conductance (mhos)	Important infrared spectral bands (cm ⁻¹)	Approx. LD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p. in mice	Gross observation at 1/5th LD ₅₀ in mice
	Metal	Carbon	Hydrogen	Nitrogen				
1. ZnSO ₄ (nic) ₂	15.86 (16.11)	35.24 (35.51)	2.81 (2.96)	13.65 (13.80)	0.7	3930 s, 3115 s, 2845 m, 1660 m, 1320 s, 1180 s, 948 m, 580 s, 450 m	464	Nil
2. ZnC ₂ O ₄ (nic) ₂	15.99 (16.45)	41.94 (42.38)	2.91 (3.02)	17.00 (17.20)	0.7	3855 s, 3105 s, 2850 m, 1715 s, 1650 s, 1975 w, 1925 s	464	decreased SMA, writhing and anoxia, hypothermia
3. Zn(NO ₃) ₂ (nic) ₂	15.00 (15.10)	38.08 (38.24)	2.59 (2.77)	19.24 (19.40)	0.9	3930 s, 3110 s, 2882 m, 1650 m, 1495 m, 1320 s, 1246 m, 1005 m	46.4	Nil
4. ZnSO ₄ (Nmpa) ₂	19.38 (19.50)	28.43 (28.65)	5.08 (5.37)	8.21 (8.35)	0.5	3275 s, 3050 s, 2825 m, 1656 m, 1185 s, 950 m, 584 s, 456 m	215	Nil
5. ZnC ₂ O ₄ (Nmpa) ₂	19.68 (19.97)	36.26 (36.68)	5.41 (5.50)	8.34 (8.56)	0.6	3270 s, 3055 s, 2880 m, 1710 s, 1680 s, 1650 m, 1380 w	>1000	Nil
6. Zn(NO ₃) ₂ (Nmpa) ₂	17.81 (17.99)	26.14 (26.48)	4.92 (4.95)	15.31 (15.40)	0.8	3275 s, 3060 s, 2795 m, 1652 m, 1490 m, 1260 m, 1010 m	140	increased SMA and reactivity, hypothermia
7. ZnSO ₄ (bza) ₂	16.01 (16.20)	41.29 (41.68)	3.36 (3.47)	6.90 (6.94)	0.5	3250 s, 3050 s, 2805 m, 1656 m, 1185 s, 940 m, 582 s, 452 m	464	Writhing, SMA decreased, atoxia reactivity decreased, anoxia
8. ZnC ₂ O ₄ (bza) ₂	16.42 (16.54)	43.31 (43.61)	3.35 (3.54)	7.00 (7.10)	0.5	3258 s, 3052 s, 2815 m, 1715 s, 1685 s, 1656 m, 1370 w	1000	Increased SMA reactivity and re piration, hypothermia
9. Zn(NO ₃) ₂ (bza) ₂	15.09 (15.15)	38.71 (38.96)	3.19 (3.24)	12.85 (12.85)	0.8	3262 s, 3060 s, 2820 m, 1650 m, 1495 m, 1250 m, 1000 m	147	SMA increased atoxia, reactivity increased, hyperthermia

with zinc through nitrogen of pyridine ring has been confirmed by considerable negative shift of about 80 cm^{-1} in CN stretching vibration of pyridine ring observed at 1400 cm^{-1} . C=O frequency of amide remains unaffected in the complexes which clearly indicates that none of the amides is coordinated with zinc through carbonyl oxygen.

Free carboxylate ion gives two asymmetric C=O bands of high intensity at 1670 and 1650 cm^{-1} and one weak symmetric C-O band at 1400 cm^{-1} . In the complexes the high frequency bands undergo positive shift and the lower frequency band suffers negative shift⁶. Thus, the ir spectral data of the complexes show bidentate nature of oxalato group.

Three bands around 1490 , 1250 and 1000 cm^{-1} observed in the ir spectra of nitrate complexes indicate that nitrate group behaves as unidentate ligand⁶. Two strong bands observed in the spectrum of Zn(II)SO_4 at 1115 and 620 cm^{-1} have been assigned as ν_2 and ν_4 modes of SO_4^{2-} ion in Td symmetry. The bands around 450 , 580 , 960 and 1130 cm^{-1} in ir spectra of all sulfato complexes have been assigned as ν_2 , ν_4 , ν_1 and ν_3 modes, respectively for unidentate sulfato group belonging to C_{2v} symmetry¹⁰.

Low molar conductance values indicate that all the complexes are nonelectrolytes in methanol and consequently confirm the presence of sulfato, nitrate and oxalato groups inside the coordination sphere.

Low LD_{50} values of nitrate complexes indicate that these are most toxic compounds of this series. The order of toxicity is nitrate > sulfato > oxalato. However, two complexes namely $[\text{ZnC}_2\text{O}_4(\text{Nmpa})_2]$ and $[\text{ZnC}_2\text{O}_4(\text{bza})_2]$ have LD_{50} values > 1000 and 1000 mg/kg ip , respectively and are almost nontoxic. Nontoxic nature of these two complexes calls for their further screening against various other pharmacological tests like antiinflammatory and anti-passive cutaneous anaphylactic activities.

Compounds No. 1, 3, 4 and 5 of Table I showed no significant effect on CNS, whereas compounds No. 2, 6, 8 and 9 acted as CNS stimulants. However, compound No. 7 exhibited depressant effect on CNS i.e. SMA and reactivity were decreased. In a few cases ataxia (due to incoordination of muscles), anoxia and writhing were observed. The structure of the complexes and CNS activity could not be correlated because of irregular trend of neurological effects.

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References

1. B. L. OSER, "Physiological Chemistry", 4th Edn., Tata Mc-Graw Hill Publishing Co., New Delhi, 1976, p. 559.

2. H. A. SCHROEDER, "Trace Elements in Nutrition", Faber and Faber, London, 1973, p. 41.
3. S. K. BAJPAI and P. R. SHUKLA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1975, 7, 21.
4. S. K. BAJPAI, K. KAR and B. N. DHAWAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1978, 47, 406.
5. S. K. BAJPAI and P. R. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 219.
6. M. MARTINETTE, S. MIZUSHIMA and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1959, 77.
7. R. G. PAUL, H. ARORA and S. L. CHANDRA, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 469.
8. S. K. BAJPAI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, 19A, 270.
9. B. M. GATEHOUSE, S. E. LIVINGSTON and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, 8, 75.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, J. FUJITA, S. TANAKA and M. KOBAYASHI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4904.

Polarographic Behaviour of N-(α -Pyridyl)-Benzaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone and Its Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Co(II), Ni(II) Complexes

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IN continuation of our stereochemical studies¹ on metal ion complexes with biologically active heterocyclic thiosemicarbazide and its substituted thiosemicarbazones, we report here the polarographic behaviour of recently synthesized and characterized N-(α -pyridyl)benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone¹ ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}$, abbreviated as PBT) which is irreversibly reduced at d.m.e. giving well defined anodic waves (pH 3.6 to 10.6) with two electron transfer electrode reaction of diffusion controlled nature. Soluble complexes of PBT with Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) are also reduced irreversibly at d.m.e. giving more negative values of $-E_{1/2}^0$. Kinetic parameters αn and $K_{1/2}^0$ are evaluated to correlate the $E_{1/2}^0$ values with ligand concentration.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of 'AnalaR' grade. Standard solutions of the metal salts were prepared in double distilled air-free conductivity water. Triple distilled mercury was used as dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.). A Leeds Northrup manual polarograph associated with Pye galvanometer and saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell through a salt bridge was used to record polarograms.

In each set 2 ml 2 M LiCl in ethanol was used as supporting electrolyte and 1.0 ml Triton-X-100 (0.2% in ethanol) was added as maxima suppressor. The volume was made up to 25 ml with ethanol and mixed thoroughly before transferring to the polarographic cell. Purified nitrogen was passed gently

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